

Ionic Equilibria of Cadmium Thiocyanate in Aqueous Solution and Related Thermodynamic Functions

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From the study of the cells of the type

$$\text{Cd}_x\text{Hg}_y \left| \begin{array}{c} \text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(m_1) \\ \text{HClO}_4(m_2) \end{array} \right| \begin{array}{c} \text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(m_1) \\ \text{HClO}_4(m_2) \end{array} \left| \begin{array}{c} \text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2(m_1) \\ \text{HClO}_4(m_2) \end{array} \right| \text{AgSCN} \left| \text{Ag} \right.$$

 the dissociation constants K_1 and K_2 corresponding to $\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdSCN}^+ + \text{SCN}^-$ and $\text{CdSCN}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{SCN}^-$ have been determined. The values of ΔH° , ΔG° and ΔS° at 25° corresponding to the above reactions have also been calculated.

A number of workers¹⁻⁸ have studied the equilibria of cadmium thiocyanate in aqueous solution by polarography, potentiometry and spectrophotometry. Recently Das and coworkers⁹ determined the dissociation constant of CdSCN^+ from the cells of the type (C_1)

In the present investigation cells of the type (C_2)

were studied.

Experimental

Double distilled water was used throughout the experiments. The experimental solutions were prepared in molalities after making necessary buoyancy corrections. Stock solution of perchloric acid was prepared from AR acid and was standardised by borax⁹. Cadmium thiocyanate was prepared¹⁰ in the laboratory. Cadmium was estimated gravimetrically by oxine and volumetrically by EDTA. Thiocyanate was estimated by silver nitrate solution. The calculated purity of cadmium thiocyanate came out to be 99.92%. It was taken to be completely pure for preparing the second stock solution containing cadmium thiocyanate mixed with perchloric acid. The experimental solutions were prepared by taking the required amount of the two stock solutions.

For silver-silver thiocyanate electrodes, silver was deposited on platinum spiral by decomposing silver oxide¹¹ and thiocyanate was deposited on it by the method of Vanderzee and Smith¹². Cadmium amalgam electrodes containing 9% cadmium were prepared by the method of LaMer and Parks¹³. The amalgam was cleaned, dried and transferred to the electrode vessel by filtering it at 60° through a washed and dried piece of muslin. The entire operations were done in atmosphere

of nitrogen. Four such electrodes thus prepared, on intercomparison gave a potential difference of less than 0.03 mv.

The cell vessels were similar to the vessel used by Prasad and coworkers¹⁴. For each solution, the duplicate cells set up agreed within 0.05 mv. Tinsley Vernier Potentiometer and air thermostat (± 0.05) were used.

Results and Discussions

The e. m. f. of the cell (C_2) is given by

$$E = E^\circ - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln a_{\text{Cd}^{++}} \cdot a^2 \text{SCN}^- \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $E^\circ = E^\circ_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgSCN}, \text{SCN}^-} - E^\circ_{\text{Cd}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Cd}^{++}}$ (Stockholm convention) $E^\circ_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgSCN}, \text{SCN}^-}$ were taken from our previous work¹⁵, and $E^\circ_{\text{Cd}_x\text{Hg}_y/\text{Cd}^{++}}$ were taken from the recalculated value by Choudhary and Prasad¹⁶.

When

$$-\log \gamma_i = \frac{AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} B_{i,\mu} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

is applied to equation (1) for activity coefficient, we get

$$E = E^\circ - \frac{2.30259RT}{2F} \left(\log m_{\text{Cd}} \cdot m^2 \text{SCN}^- - \frac{6A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + B_{i,\mu} \right) \quad (3)$$

The charges on ions have been left out for convenience. The value of A is known. The value of $B = B_{\text{Cd}} + 2B_{\text{SCN}}$ can be obtained as B is additive^{17,18} and independent of the composition of ionic atmosphere provided μ is less than 0.1 and e.m.f. accuracy > 0.1 mv.

TABLE 2—E. M. F. OF THE CELL (C₂)

$m_1 \times 10^3$	$m_2 \times 10^4$	E_{20}	E_{25}	E_{30}
4.014	3.98	0.64657	0.65074	0.65858
5.018	5.02	0.63985	0.64384	0.65155
6.017	6.06	0.63458	0.63841	0.64571
7.027	7.01	0.62997	0.63388	0.64107
8.025	8.06	0.62634	0.63004	0.63702
9.033	8.92	0.62305	0.62670	0.63363
10.017	9.96	0.62020	0.62365	0.63042
20.071	19.95	0.60322	0.60640	0.61286
22.099	22.09	0.60089	0.60402	0.61042
24.080	23.98	0.59885	0.60192	0.60828
26.110	26.74	0.59694	0.59996	0.60628
28.124	27.83	0.59520	0.59816	0.60447
30.128	29.20	0.59360	0.59654	0.60280

Assigning an arbitrary value to B and μ the corresponding value of $m_{Cd} \times m^2_{SCN}$ was calculated from the equation (3). Then corresponding value of β was calculated from equation (6) and μ from equation (7) given below :

$$\mu = (1 + 2\beta)m_1 + m_2 \quad (7)$$

Without changing B the process was repeated till a constant value of μ upto the sixth place of decimal was obtained. The corresponding value of β was provisionally taken to be correct. With these values of β and μ , m_{Cd} , m_{SCN} , m_{CdSCN} and L.H.S. of equation (5) was calculated for all experimental solutions. In the range $m_1 = 0.004$ to 0.015 when L.H.S. of equation (5) was plotted against μ , a straight line was obtained which gave the value of K_2 and B_2 . The Tables 1 and 2 do not give values between $m_1 = 0.01$ to 0.015 .

When the molalities of $Cd(SCN)_2$ exceeded 0.015 , a deviation in the linearity was observed. This led us to believe that both the complexes $CdSCN^+$ and $Cd(SCN)_2$ were present beyond $m_1 = 0.015$. Hence the e.m.f. of the cell containing solutions in the range $m_1 = 0.02$ to 0.03 were studied for the determination of K_1 . The e.m.f. together with the molalities of solutions are also given in the lower half of Tables 1 and 2.

In these solutions ($m_1 = 0.02$ to 0.03), $m_{Cd} = \alpha\beta m_1$, $m_{SCN} = \alpha(1 + \beta)m_1$, $m_{CdSCN} = (1 - \beta)\alpha m_1$ and $m_{Cd(SCN)_2} = (1 - \alpha)m_1$

$$\therefore m_{Cd} \times m^2_{SCN} = \alpha^3 \beta (1 + \beta)^2 m_1^3 \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and } K_{A(2)} = \frac{\alpha\beta(1 + \beta)m_1}{(1 - \beta)}$$

$$\therefore \frac{K^3_{A(2)}}{m_{Cd} \times m^2_{SCN}} = \frac{\beta^3(1 + \beta)}{(1 - \beta)^3} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

Since corresponding to an assigned value of B, K_2 and B_2 have already been calculated, therefore by assigning an arbitrary value to μ in equations (3) and (5) corresponding values of $m_{Cd} \times m^2_{SCN}$ and $K_{A(2)}$ were calculated for any cell solution. From equation (9), corresponding value of β was calculated and then corresponding value of α was also calculated from equation (8). For this range of solution

$$\mu = (1 + 2\beta)\alpha m_1 + m_2 \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

Hence a new value of μ was calculated from equation (10). The process was repeated till a constant value of μ upto the fifth place of decimal was obtained. The corresponding values of α and β were taken to be provisionally correct. By plotting L.H.S. of equation (4) against μ , K_1 , and B_1 were calculated.

If $B_1 + B_2 \neq B$, then the whole process was repeated by altering the value of B . When $B = 14.5$, $B_1 + B_2 = B$ (within 0.2 at all temperatures). The final values for equations (4) and (5) were calculated when the value of $B = 14.5$, Figs. 1, 2 and Table 3 correspond to this value of B .

$= \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{SCN}^-$ were calculated. Their values at 25° are 909 cal and 2702 cal respectively. When $\log K$ was plotted against $1/T$ in both cases straight lines were obtained. The values of ΔH from the plot for the above reactions are -3500 cal and 1175 cal respectively. Assuming these values equal to ΔH° at 25°, the value of ΔS° of the reactions at 25° come out to be -14.8 cal degree⁻¹ mole⁻¹ and 5.1 cal degree⁻¹ mole⁻¹ respectively.

The values of ΔH of reaction $\text{CdSCN}^+ = \text{Cd}^{++} + \text{SCN}^-$ as reported by Das and coworkers⁸ is 3430 and that by Nancollas and Torrance²⁰ is 700. The difference between our and Das and coworkers⁸ value may be due

TABLE 3—FINAL RESULTS WHEN $B=14.5$

Temp.°C	$K_1 \times 10^3$	$K_2 \times 10^3$	B_1	B_2
15	26.4	0.973	0.45	14.25
20	23.1	1.016	0.36	14.30
25	21.5	1.041	0.44	13.94
30	20.0	1.077	0.39	13.90
35	17.4	1.122	0.38	14.11

TABLE 4—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS FROM LITERATURE.

Name of authors	$K_1 \times 10^3$	$K_2 \times 10^3$
Laden'	1.05(25°)	4.1 (25°)
Hume, DeFord and Cave ⁹	1.8 (30°)	9.1 (30°)
Turyan and Serova ⁸		1.82(25°)
Doot and Karmalkar ⁴	1.35(25°)	9.1 (25°)
Vasilev and Mukhina ⁵		3.11(25°)
Oga and coworkers ⁶	2.14 ± 0.24	7.8 ± 1.5
Das and coworkers ⁸		0.71(25°)
		0.78(30°)
		0.85(35°)
		1.82(45°)

The difference (4%) in the values of B calculated by the two methods is perhaps due to the fact that insignificant amounts of CdBr_2 and $\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2$ were present when they were assumed to be absent.

The values of K_1 and K_2 determined by different authors are given in Table 4.

The difference in the values of K_1 as well as K_2 of the various workers is very large. Most of the workers have not taken activity coefficient into account. Das and his workers⁸ have taken them into account but they have used Davis equation for activity coefficient. Liquid junction potential in their cell might not have been completely eliminated. Their values are still nearest to our values. Since in our work, activity coefficient has been taken into account and hydrolysis has been prevented by addition of HClO_4 , our values may be taken to be most accurate values obtained so far.

Related Thermodynamic Functions

From the values of dissociation constants ΔG° of the reactions $\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2 = \text{CdSCN}^+ + \text{SCN}^-$ and CdSCN^+

to the reasons already explained. It is quite possible that the lower value of Nancollas and Torrance²⁰ may be due to (i) appreciable amounts of $\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2$ in their solutions, as m_1 in their case goes upto 0.06 and (ii) K_2 values of Vasilev and Mukhina⁵ were used by them.

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